

USING AI-BASED TOOLS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' CONFIDENCE IN SPEAKING ENGLISH

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Abstract. Many students find speaking in English difficult, not only because of grammar or vocabulary, but also because they are not confident. This is very common among B1-level learners. They often understand the language, but when it comes to speaking, they hesitate. This paper looks at how artificial intelligence (AI) tools can help students feel more confident when speaking. Today, many learners use chatbots and other AI tools to practice English. From what I have seen, students feel more relaxed when they speak with AI because they are not afraid of making mistakes. This can help them speak more often and improve step by step. The paper also discusses why confidence is important and how it affects speaking performance.

Keywords: confidence, speaking, AI tools, learners, communication

Introduction

Speaking in English is not always easy for students. Even if they know grammar rules or have enough vocabulary, they may still feel uncomfortable when they try to speak. I have noticed this especially with B1-level learners. They often stop while speaking or avoid speaking at all. The main reason is not always lack of knowledge, but lack of confidence.

Many students are afraid of making mistakes. They think others will judge them, so they prefer to stay quiet. According to Stephen Krashen (1982), emotions like fear and anxiety can affect language learning. When students feel stressed, they cannot use the language freely.

In normal classroom situations, not every student gets enough chance to speak. Some students are active, but others stay silent. Because of this, it is important to find other ways to help them practice.

Nowadays, artificial intelligence is becoming more popular in education. Tools like chatbots give students a chance to practice speaking anytime. They can try again and again without feeling embarrassed. This paper tries to explain how such tools can help students feel more confident when speaking English.

Theoretical Background

Confidence is one of the key factors in speaking. If a student feels confident, they will try to speak even if they make mistakes. If not, they may avoid speaking completely.

Motivation is also connected to confidence. Zoltán Dörnyei (2001) explains that students who are motivated usually participate more. In my opinion, confidence grows when students have more practice and feel comfortable.

Another important idea comes from Lev Vygotsky (1978), who said that learning happens through interaction. This means students need to communicate to improve their language skills. But in reality, not all students are ready to speak in front of others.

This is where technology can be helpful. AI tools can create simple conversations and respond to students. According to Chapelle (2001), technology can support language learning in interactive ways. Also, Godwin-Jones (2018) mentions that digital tools make learning more interesting and engaging.

Methodology

This study looks at B1-level students who are not confident in speaking. Many of them hesitate, speak very little, or avoid communication.

To help them, AI-based tools were used. Students practiced speaking with chatbots. They answered questions, had short conversations, and talked about daily topics.

The tasks were simple and close to real life. For example, students talked about their daily routine, hobbies, or plans. They also practiced asking and answering questions.

One important thing is that students could practice alone. They did not feel pressure, so they were more relaxed. They could repeat sentences and correct themselves.

To see the results, students were observed before and after using AI tools. Their confidence and participation were compared.

Results and Discussion

After some time, students started to change. They became more confident and less afraid of speaking. They tried to speak more, even if their sentences were not perfect.

Some students said that practicing with AI was easier than speaking in class. They felt free and did not worry about mistakes. This helped them speak more often.

Another thing I noticed is that students became more active in lessons. They answered questions more and joined discussions. This shows that confidence really affects speaking.

Also, students practiced more outside the classroom. Since AI tools are easy to use, they could practice anytime. This made a big difference.

However, AI is not perfect. It cannot replace a teacher. Teachers are still needed to guide students and explain mistakes. In my opinion, using both AI and classroom teaching together gives better results.

Conclusion

To sum up, confidence is very important in learning to speak English. Many B1 students struggle not because they do not know the language, but because they are afraid to use it.

AI tools can help solve this problem. They give students a chance to practice in a relaxed way. Students feel less pressure and become more confident.

From what I see, combining traditional lessons with AI tools is a good idea. It can help students become more active and improve their speaking step by step.

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